

Title: EDUCATION IN THE CONSTITUTION OF CÁDIZ. A REVIEW FROM GRAMSCI'S PERSPECTIVE

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Keywords: Cadiz, Hegemony, Constitution, Domination, Class.

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Resumé : L'article discute de l'application de l'étude de Gramsci à la première Constitution espagnole. The educational and class aspects are observed here.

Mots-clé: Cadiz, L'hégémonie, la Constitution, Domination, la Classe.

EDUCATION IN THE CONSTITUTION OF CADIZ. A REVIEW FROM GRAMSCI'S PERSPECTIVE

Two hundred years after the promulgation of the Constitution of 1812, at the time of its commemoration, it is necessary to reflect on the implications that the Magna Carta had on Spanish education. The historical literature has dealt extensively with this period, revealing the relationships between society and education at the time (Puelles, 2004; Aranque, 2009). However, the sociological literature usually focused on the present day, has not paid attention to the internal processes and the event. In an attempt to shed new light on the phenomenon, we suggest here the conceptual perspective and analysis of Antonio Gramsci that can unveil unaddressed processes. In that sense, this article is the application, at least in its vision of Gramscian study, to the references contained in the 1812 Cadiz Constitution on education.

The first non-statal Spanish Magna Carta had a brief and disruptive life; after its promulgation, it was only in force for two years, being subsequently rehabilitated on two occasions, between 1820 and 1823 and between 1836 and 1837, and was hardly implemented as a result of these circumstances, reflecting the political vicissitudes of the time. Despite this, its importance is unquestionable both because of the rule imposed on the subsequent constitutional development of the liberal bourgeoisie and what would derive from it, such as the configuration of new citizenship disseminated and expressed through other institutions.

As for Antonio Gramsci, his short life contrasts with his prolific work and offers an enormous wealth of concepts which, far from becoming obsolete, in the light of new developments, become more relevant with time. In the same way, their application to past events continues to generate their interpretation. In the present case, we consider that the concepts elaborated by Gramsci apply to the study of the Constitution and its era, providing explanatory and not merely descriptive resources to a part of our history. Gramsci's work is of special interest for the study of social structure, since one of his contributions is the examination of the "hegemonic segment or bloc" of societies through the observation of institutions and social groups; the tensions between civil society and the State and the relations of force between social classes; as well as the study of social change from the point of view of hegemony. It is also a reference for a critical interpretation of education. However, we are aware that Gramsci's conceptual richness and the development of studies on the Magna Carta of Cadiz are taking place on the occasion of its bicentenary, which would allow for a more detailed and acute analysis.

1.- BRIEF REFERENCE TO GRAMSCI'S BIOGRAPHY

Gramsci is not a sociologist, but he is an intellectual with a tremendous sociological perspective, perhaps because he was a brilliant student and a life full of difficulties: the precarious economic condition of his youth was combined with an ungraceful physique, deteriorated by an accident he suffered as a child followed by inadequate care. As we know, the greater the degree of social marginalization, the greater the possibility of developing a sociological temperament (Macionis and Plummer, 2000: 12). Gramsci is also a great political activist; co-founder of the Italian Communist Party in 1921; his militancy will cost him his life. Only by understanding his double consideration as an intellectual and a man of action can we know his thought, which stands out for three traits: the constant use of historical materialism as an interpretative key, his permanent link with reality, and his continuous defense of those who suffer.

The Italian takes as its starting point Marx's distinction between superstructure and infrastructure and the explanation he gives as to why an oppressed social class not only remains in such a situation but also participates in it: what subjugates us is presented as a power granted by nature, and so people tend to reify it, believing that it is external to them and therefore, that it cannot be changed. The unequal forces and relations of production are thus maintained.

Gramsci focuses his work on the cultural aspects of society, the superstructure, precisely to unveil how political action can be taken to end the hegemony of the capitalist bourgeoisie. This hegemony is a fundamental concept in Gramscian interpretation. Like Marx and Engels, Gramsci understands hegemony as the domination of civil society by the ruling class. Hegemony translates into the ideological domination of a social class's values, morals, and general conception of the world and of man. In other words, power is mainly based on the cultural hegemony that the dominant classes exercise over the dominated classes.

2.- A PROPOSAL: THE STUDY OF THE CONSTITUTION OF 1812 FOLLOWING GRAMSCI'S ANALYSIS

The Cadiz Constitution of 1812 represents the legal, political, and ultimately apparent triumph of the liberal bourgeoisie for the first time in Spain. The Constitution of Cadiz is the legal expression of a series of values that a social class, the bourgeoisie, tries to impose on Spanish society after having acquired class consciousness. However, let us not forget that in that same Spanish society, bourgeois values do not predominate either quantitatively or qualitatively. The Cadiz Constitution is bourgeois because the very historical fact that makes it Cadiz, the War of Independence, has meant that the deputies who will sit in the Cortes do not represent all the lands of the Kingdom of Spain. For this reason, the representatives of regions with strong ties to the Ancien Régime, such as Castile and Aragon, to name but a few, were replaced by elements of the Cádiz bourgeoisie, which was much more cosmopolitan, enterprising, and liberal than the inland estates, especially the privileged ones.

For these reasons, the bourgeois hegemonic triumph was only apparent. In reality, the privileged groups of the ancien régime continued to hold social and political predominance, even if they had to begin to make certain concessions. Throughout the 19th century, a process of osmosis and interpenetration of the bourgeois and aristocratic classes took place. Applying Gramscian terminology, we could say that the Cadiz Constitution events visualize the struggle for control of the hegemony between an emerging category that tries to impose itself and a ruling class that is gradually losing this position. The definitive triumph of bourgeois values does not come about because they are embodied in a Constitution but through the conciliation of a pact constructed little by little. The former privileged classes continue to retain, *de facto*, a large part of their economic power and social predominance.

There are also certain parallels between the general social condition of Spanish society and that of Italy in terms of the impossibility of forging alliances between progressive and peasant forces. This contrasts with what happened in France, where the peasantry was the social base of a party that radically opposed the ancien régime. Thus, what the Constitution of 1812 would establish would be the beginning of "a peaceful consensus," which would make other kinds of political and social reforms possible.

Returning to Gramsci's thought, for there to be a real replacement of dominant classes by other emerging classes, there must be a crisis of hegemony, a war of positions, and an active

positioning of intellectuals. A crisis of hegemony is arrived at by the unpopularity of acts of dominant classes, as well as by the activism of an emerging, previously passive group. A war of position consists of a non-frontal strategic attack similar to guerrilla warfare, as opposed to a frontal attack on the State's central power where there is a social, ideological, and political confrontation, which only occurs in exceptional circumstances. The war of position aims to encircle the state apparatus by empowering a dominated group through its organizations, institutions, and the development of a culture. According to Gramsci, any social group, before gaining the power to govern, must exercise social and cultural leadership. In the conditions of modern society, Gramsci thought, a class does not maintain its social domination by the exclusive use of physical violence and juridical violence, i.e., "material force" and "force of law." It also needs the active consensus of most individuals and social groups that make up civil society. See that Gramsci distinguishes between directing society (which is that social and cultural leadership that provides an active social consensus) and the exercise of government or rule.

As we have explained above, the Constitution drawn up by the Cortes of Cadiz is the result of very particular conditions that do not reflect the real weight of social forces and where bourgeois progressiveness is over-represented, so it is not surprising, in view of Gramsci's argument, that the Constitution was never deployed as a tool of government, which would amount to the government of an emerging social class without its values and ideas being taken on board and internalized by society as a whole. In other words, the Cortes of Cadiz would be an example of the failure of social domination without prior social leadership: the bourgeoisie legislated without having previously deployed social leadership.

To achieve this, it is necessary to have the help of certain social mechanisms specialized in the social production of active consensus. The specialists in the social manufacture of hegemony are the intellectuals themselves and the independent schools where the necessary cadres can be trained.

Our author devotes a large part of his work to the work of intellectuals, distinguishing on the one hand between being an intellectual and acting as such and, on the other, between the traditional intellectual and the organic intellectual. As for the first distinction, for Gramsci, intellectuals cannot be defined as such by the work they do but by the social role they play. It must be said that our author is generous when it comes to establishing who are intellectuals, understanding that, to the extent that each person uses his or her brain capacity to a greater or lesser degree, he or she can be so considered. To exercise as such, however, implies leading both technically and politically a group, either the already dominant one or another that aspires to it (Monasta, 1993: 663). This ties in with the second distinction, that between traditional and organic intellectuals. Traditional intellectuals are distinguished by their historical continuity and relative social autonomy; in practice, they contribute to the fabrication of the social hegemony of the "ruling class." Any group that aspires to become a ruling class cannot achieve this hegemony if it has only the traditional intellectuals to assimilate. It also needs other specialists capable of directing the new social activities: the organic intellectuals. Organic intellectuals have the function of leading society intellectually and morally through education and culture and not through traditional legal and police coercion (Monasta, 1993: 648). Gramscian theory on

intellectuals, as well as addressing the lack of understanding of the role and importance of the intelligentsia in the socialist movement, has the function of criticizing the idealist view of intellectuals as a group that "exists above and outside the relations of production"; of highlighting the involvement of this collective in the reproduction of the system of social relations; and of "establishing the essential characteristics of intellectual activity in its relation to the existence and reproduction of the social whole" (Acanda, 2002).

All these considerations are made by Gramsci concerning late capitalism, aiming to establish the strategy to be followed by the working class and its allies to replace the predominance of the bourgeoisie. We can make a correspondence about the circumstances at the time of the drafting of the Constitution, although in this case, it is the old privileged classes of the privileged classes that are to be eclipsed.

As for the authors of the Magna Carta, there is no doubt that when the deputies took part in drafting it, it can be said that they were not only authors but also intellectuals, which can be said of most but not all of them since there was the figure of the deputy who never took part in the debates and limited himself to voting, giving rise to the term *culiparlante*, which became part of the Cádiz vernacular (Payán, 2000). As for the categorization of their lordships as one type of intellectual or another, it is possible to make a simple distinction between those who hold liberal positions that imply the rise of the bourgeoisie and those who fight for the maintenance of the status quo. The former included the civil servants, who represented a quarter of the composition of the chamber and who for Palacio Atard (quoted by García León, 2009b: 124) formed "the sociological support of the liberalism of Cadiz." Among the latter, it is worth noting the representatives of the privileged groups, mainly from the ecclesiastical and military establishment, who accounted for almost half of the deputies in the Cortes (García León, 2009b: 125). However, this simplification obscures the variety and singularity of each case. On the one hand, the range of ideas is very varied and sometimes even extreme. Thus, we can find both deputies described as revolutionaries, as in the case of the Ecuadorian Mejía Lequerica, and declared and staunch absolutists. To such an extent that some deputies who disagreed with the liberal wording of the Constitution were even reluctant to sign it or refused to do so outright. In the end, they were forced to do so by the approval of a proposal that ostracised and banished those who did not sign it (García León, 2009: 187-192).

On the other hand, neither is included in a professional group a guarantee that one will opt for bourgeois liberalism or traditionalism. If this had been the case, with the numbers we have discussed, the result would not have been what it was. Thus we find liberal clerics as important in the development of the Cortes as Muñoz Torrero or Nicasio Gallego.

In any case, the large ecclesiastical representation explains why the Constitution, despite being more liberal than the society it represented and cutting back on some of the prerogatives of the traditional powers, did not break with them. The references to the Catholicity of the kingdom and the framing of the Cortes in religious rites are constant and contrast with the spirit of Joseph Bonaparte's laws, which were much more belligerent towards religion. Throughout the Spanish 19th century, however, the neo-Stalinist groups gradually acquired a notable preponderance that allowed them to occupy the main posts not only in the University but also in the State's civil

administration. It could be said that the establishment or consolidation of this type of intellectuals took place later. Although it deviates from our work, it should be noted that the Constitution of 1856 during the progressive biennium would re-establish an earlier constitution, that of 1837, but with a more liberal-progressive orientation. In the end, it was not promulgated.

As shown in the historical event under study, intellectuals for Gramsci are vital for the construction of a culture of political self-management: the society of the moment needs the inspiration of representatives. Unorganized, the masses neither think nor solve. In spite of the differences described between the deputies, they are de facto privileged in the definition and formulation of the rights of a people who, according to their dedication, are already conformed as "Citizenship." As Gramsci says (Díaz Salazar, 1991: 426), political action "requires a new man and aims to favour the emergence of a new humanity." The role of intellectuals will be to modernize the structures, and this is possible with the development of educational institutions that will also serve as catalysts of the ideological and social modernity that the Constitution seeks to establish.

3.- THE STUDY OF THE EDUCATIONAL QUESTION

So far, we have seen how Gramsci emphasizes "the value of cultural facts as shapers of man in the creation of his own history" (Noguera, 2011: 1-4). Precisely, both education and Gramsci's idea of generating a change in people, their ideas, and their economic position are linked to the birth of the modern State. Having analyzed Gramscian concepts of social hegemony and the role of intellectuals in it, we compare the formulation of a new educational project in Gramsci's theoretical formulation with that of the Constitution of 1812.

The Constitution's references to educational matters are condensed into six articles, including form title nine: De la instrucción pública (On public instruction). The first of the articles, 366, states that:

In all the towns of the Monarchy, schools of first letters shall be established, in which children shall be taught to read, write and count, and the catechism of the Catholic religion, which shall also include a brief exposition of civil obligations.

The establishment of primary schools in all the towns of the Monarchy would have been an important extension of education in the country. It is possible that the deputies who drafted the Constitution, most of them educated and learned men, could see the need for such an extension. However, the wording of the article does not make education compulsory and does not incorporate women into this fundamental right. In this latter respect, Joseph Bonaparte's instruction draft was more advanced, which, in line with Condorcet's thinking, recognized the equal rights of men and women in this section. In terms of equal access to education for boys and girls, Josephine legislation surpassed that of Napoleon (Aranque, 2009: 8). It must be said that before the Cadiz and Bonaparte regulations, even before the French Revolution, there were enlightened voices in Spain that advocated this recognition, such as Josefina Amar y Borbón,

who in 1769 had already published the *Discurso sobre la educación física y moral de las mujeres* and who later wrote *Importancia de la instrucción que conviene dar a las mujeres* (Importance of the instruction that should be given to women) (1784). But there were not only voices; the Cortes of Navarre of 1780-1781 issued regulations for the establishment of an incipient network of girls' schools, and those of 1794-1797 corrected, completed, and developed some of these aspects.

The struggle between discriminatory continuity and the most radical liberal egalitarianism can be seen in the legislative changes that followed: in the session of 9 September 1813, the universality of education was determined, and in 1814, a ruling was discussed in the Cortes "maintaining reticence towards the inclusion of women in the creation of public schools and once again consolidating the bases of the differences between the sexes," as it envisaged a domestic education for girls in accordance with the role assigned to them by the privacy of the home (Ruiz-Rico, 2012: 8).

As Ruiz-Rico (2012: 14) concludes in an article on the situation of women in the Magna Carta of Cádiz: "The Constitution of 1812 meant a social and legal continuity with respect to women, in a scenario of legal inferiority based on the Napoleonic civil code and without interest in reforming the discriminatory situation of the female sex. A historic opportunity was lost at a propitious moment of liberal and egalitarian euphoria to make some juridical and political concessions to women".

Gramsci would be in favor of the universality of education mainly for two reasons: the first for a question of democratic opportunity or social justice and the second for the function he gives to education itself as an expression and motor of the social. As for the first, he criticizes the fact that although all citizens pay taxes, opportunities are more favorable to the bourgeoisie, with secondary and higher education being more available to the mediocre children of the bourgeoisie than to the able children of the proletariat. It is understood that at the time Gramsci is living, primary education is already accessible to the majority of the population, but the reasoning would be transferable to primary education in Spain at the beginning of the 19th century.

Gramsci's allusions to the situation of women are not about education but about their place in the system of production. Gramsci's ideas on women and the mode of production are very interesting, but to deal with them now would take away the object of the present work.

Gramsci's other reason for defending the universality of education is the improvement of society, a point on which he agrees with the constitutionalists of 1812. But our author goes much further in understanding that the cultural elevation of the people is a problem to be solved, being more critical for culture to reach the masses than for a minority to possess a great deal of knowledge (Gramsci, 1997). But in addition, the extension of education is linked to selecting great leaders and creating a new culture in opposition to the hegemonic bourgeois culture.

As for the contents of primary education, article 366 of the Constitution has many similarities with Gramsci's description of the first grade of the single school. Both begin by considering instrumental culture as essential: reading, writing, elementary arithmetic. However, Gramsci also pays special attention to the rights and duties of everyone, while the Magna Carta, although it includes civil obligations as a subject, forgets about rights. In addition, Gramsci adds a general notion of the human environment and its history, and something fundamental for him, the concept of work as the latent and unitary key to primary schools. For his part, in the Constitution, he introduced the catechism of the Catholic religion at this stage. This would form part of the "cultural battle" described by Gramsci (Coutinho: 2007). In short, the education described in the article does not describe a complete school system, much less a unitary one, as Gramsci would have wanted. According to Gramsci, this minimal instruction would serve for the implantation of a type of hegemony, the bourgeois one, since from his perspective, all relations of domination are above all ideological relations and pedagogical relations.

None of the six articles dedicated to education in the Magna Carta refers to secondary education, which is fundamental in Gramscian theory of education because it is at this level that social differences begin to become evident. Article 367 alone states that:

Likewise, the competent number of Universities and other establishments of instruction that are judged convenient for teaching all sciences, literature, and fine arts shall be arranged and created.

The proposal to create centers for science, literature, and the fine arts is a very general objective. The desire of the bourgeoisie to enlighten the majority of the population will remain at the primary level, and only the bourgeoisie will have access to higher levels. The middle class will be able to opt for professional training. Gramsci is very critical of bourgeois education in this respect. In the search for equal opportunities for all, the Italian defends the single school. That is the same education for all social strata, eliminating the class orientation of schooling, putting an end to the opposition between general culture and professional instruction, between schools for elites and schools for artisans. For Gramsci, the distinction between manual labor and intellectual labor diverts attention to technical aspects of labor, concealing its ideological character.

In Article 368, we find two differentiated messages, the first of which is particularly important. It reads:

'The general plan of teaching shall be uniform throughout the kingdom, the political Constitution of the Monarchy having to be explained in all Universities and literary establishments where ecclesiastical and political sciences are taught.

The references made in the Cortes to the unity of Spain are frequent. They are not only justified by the historical situation of confrontation with a common enemy. They also reveal a project for a state with twinned territories and without privileges.

The approach of uniform education is in line with that of Gramsci, given the references, we find in the author in this respect: the school makes it possible for the pupil to overcome the particularist social sentiments resulting from the influence of the social or local environment.

The second part of the article is more difficult to interpret. States often make an effort to ensure that their citizens know the basic principles they are governed and condensed in their Constitution. We can find this throughout history in many states, including ours today. What is remarkable here is that it is included in such a general norm as a Constitution. The Gramscian interpretation of this measure would be related to the dissemination and consolidation of the hegemonic culture that has been able to draft the Magna Carta. However, as we have seen above, in reality, in the case in question, this was the culture that was doing battle with the still hegemonic one.

Articles 369 and 370 limits themselves to defining who will be in charge of designing and inspecting instruction. The first of the aforementioned reads:

There shall be a General Directorate of Studies, composed of persons of known instruction, in charge of which shall be under the government's authority, the inspection of public education.

And 370 states:

Using unique plans and statutes, the Cortes shall arrange everything about the critical object of public instruction.

For the enlightened members of the chamber, education was so important that it could not be left to chance or to private initiative, even if the latter had a place under the supervision of the competent authority. Nor is this anything new, as local councils and governments had to give the go-ahead for the establishment of centers or new programs. But two issues should be highlighted. The first is that, despite the numerical importance of the deputies belonging to the clergy, the Cortes continues to be given the power to set the programs and statutes of the universities, in keeping with the centralization of education as a public service and not as a service controlled by the Church. The second is that the setting of competencies should be raised to the highest normative rank.

Gramsci did not question the ability of those in power to act in this area, but he also gave the masses their role and made organization dependent on the creation of the new culture. For him, education is an organized and political task, and therefore he does not believe that education

should be carried out in an improvised or spontaneous manner. Nor does this imply that it should be imposed, as this would be neither effective nor lasting, characteristics that require intellectual and moral direction in order to be realized. Interesting in this respect is his idea that deduction is not the dissemination of ideas from above but a process in which the mass and the top educate each other. It is precisely this relationship that is the way to create a new culture, which in Gramsci's case will be the new workers' culture.

The ninth title of the Constitution, on public instruction, closes with an emblematic article, 371, dedicated to freedom, which reads as follows:

All Spaniards are free to write, print, and publish their political ideas without the need for any license, revision, or approval prior to publication, under the restrictions and responsibility established by law.

The meaning of the inclusion of this article in the chapter of the Constitution dedicated to public instruction is understood by the deputies' conception of it as enlightenment, an education, a measure for citizens (Ramos Santana, 2010:21) which favors freedom of expression and thought. In a brief preamble to Decree no. 9 of the Cortes Generales meeting in the Isla de León, it is stated that "the individual faculty of citizens to publish their thoughts and political ideas (...) is a means of enlightening the Nation in general, and the only way to lead to the knowledge of true public opinion". Freedom of the press was a necessity for two-thirds of the House, 66 deputies voted in favor and 31 against. As stated in the Conciso of 4 October when Ferdinand VII returned: "if there is no public opinion and the means to re-establish it freely, he will ruin the Cortes and the nation whenever he wishes." To fully understand the significance of this article, it must be borne in mind that the freedom to disseminate ideas is reactive that precipitates the enjoyment of other freedoms by the population and that, beyond leading to freedom of thought, it does not end until the freedom of action is achieved within socially established limits.

By the time Gramsci writes, it has already become clear that public opinion is not alien to power, even when there is a considerable degree of freedom of the press. For Gramsci, the media are, along with the educational system and religious institutions, the instruments through which the dominant classes make the subordinate classes experience their condition as natural, inhibiting their revolutionary potential. According to this approach, the media, like education, require the co-participation of the masses in order to bring about the creation of a new culture. This is not a spontaneous task but a directed one. A dilemma thus arises between freedom and direction.

Gramsci reflects on this dilemma precisely on the educational level. He does not deny freedom but understands that it can only occur within a directed and disciplined action. "Discipline and freedom do not contradict each other, but quite the contrary: there is no freedom, there is no properly human individual, except insofar as this freedom is the product of discipline." This idea is not original to Gramsci. One of the fathers of sociology, Durkheim, considered that a condition for the enjoyment of individual freedom is the existence of morality that acts as a form of social control. Without the existence of moral bonds, Durkheim would say, man, becomes a slave to his increasingly ambitious and insatiable passions. Gramsci's thought will vehemently defend

these precepts against an individualistic and biologicistic vision which proposes to renounce the formation of the child in order to allow his personality to develop freely. What we now know about the social formation of the personality overturns the latter approach and recognizes the veracity of Gramscian statements. It must be said that direction for Gramsci is not the same as external coercion and force, a model of education which he calls Jesuitical and which he also criticizes (Laso, 1991).

4.- FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

At this point, it can therefore be said that Gramscian terminology can be applied to the analysis of a historical event such as the Constitution of 1812. In its support, it will be said that concepts are the basis for observing processes from other perspectives, which can open up the referential framework and at the same time the analysis of other terms which participate and coincide in the aspect analyzed or enunciate risky ideas which allow us further reflections. In the present case, concepts such as hegemonic groups and education are mentioned, as well as others that derive from them, such as the norm that is promulgated, bourgeois values, or the moral sphere. The difference between the norm and the civil society from which it is enunciated, the advances of laws with respect to the realities from which they emerge, and how these laws can slow down or speed up social processes of another type (political, civic, moral), are also evident in this analysis. The application of these concepts to the study of the norm that is produced (the Constitution) also allows us to conclude some considerations regarding the treatment of education.

Like Gramsci, we have asked ourselves about the social role of political events, in this case, the drafting of a Constitution. The function of the Constitution is not only political but also social by connecting and gathering the interests of a social class. It is clear that there is a social function in terms of the conquests it aims to achieve and those it did, in fact, achieve: to set itself up as the beginning of the reflection and analysis of the duties and rights of the people in Spain. But at the same time, according to Gramsci, it produces a new subjectivity (Díaz Salazar, 1991: 427), a new morality or perspective not previously contemplated. This new subjectivity becomes real, in the case we are studying, with the right to education promulgated by the Constitution. As we have seen, education will contribute to this process once it is legitimized and consolidated as such.

The construction of the Constitution cannot be carried out without legislators, just as the construction of equality cannot be carried out without the Constitution in modern times. At the same time, citizenship is configured and legitimized. It is a concern that has long been imagined and which is now becoming apparent in this period.

Our intention has been to continue reflecting on civil and political society and to invite to do so, and we hope that the desire to do so has been aroused.

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